

Granular insecticides for controlling brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH)

S. Uthamasamy and S. Suresh, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612 101, India

BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Dist.) cause heavy losses in Jun-Sep in Thanjavur District. In 1984, we compared four granular insecticides with carbofuran for

BPH and GLH control. Treatments (see table) were arranged in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications in 30- m² plots planted with ADT31. Insecticides were broadcast in 5.0 cm standing water 10 and 40 d after transplanting (DT) and impounded for 48 h. BPH and GLH adults and nymphs were counted in 10 randomly selected hills/plot at 20, 35, and 50 DT.

Insecticide-treated plots had lower insect populations than the untreated

check. Carbofuran 3 G at 1.0 kg ai/ ha effectively reduced BPH population. Ethoprop 10G effectively reduced GLH on 20 and 35 DT, and on 50 DT bromophos ethyl plots had fewest GLH. Carbofuran-treated plots yielded 4.8 t/ha compared with 3.2 t/ha for the untreated check. Increase in yields in Benfuracarb- and carbofuran- treated plots may be due to phytotonic effect. *S*

Mean incidence of brown planthopper and green leafhopper, and grain yield after application of granular insecticides.^a

Treatment	Formulation	Dose (kg ai/ha)	BPH (no./hill)			GLH (no./hill)			Grain yield (t/ha)
			20 DAT	35 DAT	50 DAT	20 DAT	35 DAT	50 DAT	
Benfuracarb	3 G	1.5	0.66 ab	5.66 ab	22.66 ab	4.33 ab	8.33 ab	8.66 ab	4.1 b
Bromophos ethyl	5 G	1.5	1.66 b	11.33 b	18.00 ab	3.66 ab	11.33 ab	6.00 a	2.9 c
Ethoprop	10 G	1.5	2.00 b	5.66 ab	27.00 b	3.00 a	7.66 a	8.66 ab	3.2 c
Quinalphos	3 G	1.5	1.00 ab	7.33 b	34.00 b	3.33 ab	12.33 b	10.00 b	2.8 c
Carbofuran	3 G	1.0	0.33 a	4.33 a	14.00 a	3.33 ab	8.00 ab	6.33 ab	4.8 a
(standard check)									
Untreated control	-	-	3.00 c	12.00 b	57.33 c	11.00 c	17.66 c	20.00 c	3.2 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different. DAT = days after treatment.

Beauveria bassiana for controlling brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH)

Li Hongke, Institute of Plant Protection, Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Changsha, China

We studied the host range of *B. bassiana* on rice insects. The fungus was isolated from 17 insect species of 6 orders, and occurred most frequently on BPH and GLH.

We evaluated *B. bassiana* for controlling BPH and GLH in the field. Four fungus isolates were tested in 40- × 40- × 100-cm cages covering 4 hills of rice. GLH were placed in the cages and

treated with dusts containing 11 × 10⁸ *B. bassiana* conidia/g (see table). In a similar experiment, BPH mortality was

60-90% 15 d after treatment. GLH was more susceptible to *B. bassiana* than BPH. *S*

GLH and BPH mortality after *B. bassiana* infection.

Isolate origin	Mortality (%)	
	7d after treatment	10 d after treatment
GLH	78	96
BPH (1)	67	92
BPH (2)	65	91
<i>C. suppressalis</i>	60	91
Control	0	8

Influence of nitrogen fertilizer level and timing on stem borer (SB) incidence

M.S. Purohit, P.M. Bhatt, A.H. Shah, and S. Raman, National Agricultural Research Project (NARP), Gujarat Agricultural University, Navsari 396450, India

We evaluated the influence on SB incidence of four N sources at three

application levels and two timings at NARP in summer 1985.

IR22 seedlings were transplanted in 7.2-m² plots in a split-plot design with 3 replications. No insecticides were applied. Percent deadhearts and total tillers in 30 hills/plot were recorded 50 d after transplanting.

SB damage was significantly lower when N was applied as ammonium sulfate (see table). *S*

Influence of N fertilizer source, level, and timing on SB damage,^a Navsari, India, 1985.

N source	SB deadhearts (%)						Av (%)
	100 kg N/ha		80 kg N/ha		60 kg N/ha		
	T1	T2	T1	T2	T1	T2	
Ammonium sulfate	11	12	10	18	17	21	15
Urea	13	21	30	24	27	15	22
Neem cake-coated urea	16	15	21	21	22	16	19
Urea supergranules	30	11	14	12	20	14	17
Mean	17.50	14.92	19.08	18.90	21.74	16.97	
CD for N source	3.3		ns		ns		
CD for level and time	ns		ns		ns		
CD for interaction	10.1		ns		ns		

^aT1 = basal application, T2 = 50% basal + 50% 20 d after transplanting.